

INTERNET PLATFORM AS A DIDACTIC TOOL FOR DISTANCE TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: the article is devoted to the problem of creating an Internet platform for English teachers; such an Internet platform is considered by the author as an innovative didactic tool that performs all the functions of didactic tools and can be used for distance learning English to a group of students; Characterizing the existing Internet platforms, the author comes to the conclusion that the proposed options do not meet the needs of foreign language teachers.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola ingliz tili o'qituvchilari uchun Internet platformasini yaratish muammosiga bag'ishlangan; bunday Internet-platforma muallif tomonidan didaktik vositalarning barcha funktsiyalarini bajaradigan va ingliz tilida masofaviy ta'lim uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan innovatsion didaktik vosita sifatida qaraladi; mavjud internet platformalarini tavsiflaydi.

Аннотация: данная статья посвящена проблеме создания интернет-платформы для преподавателей английского языка; такого рода интернет-платформа рассматривается автором как инновационное дидактическое средство, выполняющая все функции дидактических средств и может быть использована для дистанционного обучения английскому языку; характеризуются имеющиеся интернет-платформы.

Keywords: didactic tool, Internet platform, e-learning, distance learning of a foreign language.

In the modern world, there is an urgent need to use information technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language, as they allow not only to facilitate the process itself, but also to expand the audience of students. The ability to use an Internet

platform for classes allows the teacher to conduct a full lesson in real time using the resources of the Internet platform. However, most teachers are wary of this type of teaching, preferring a traditional lesson to the latest technology.

This article will focus on the Internet platform as a didactic tool for teaching a foreign language in additional education. Our task is to compare traditional didactic tools and their functions and the Internet platform as an innovative tool, to identify their role in the modern process of teaching foreign languages.

The concept of a didactic tool is considered both in a narrow and in a broad sense. According to the opinion of V.A. Slastenin, didactic means are objects that are sensorimotor stimuli that affect the students' senses and facilitate their direct and indirect knowledge of the world [4, p. 276]. According to the author, didactic tools include all objects used in the educational process and facilitating the process itself, such as textbooks, school supplies, computers, etc. We are interested in a broader understanding of the very concept of a didactic tool.

Traditional material didactic means are usually classified according to sensory modality [2]. That is, based on which sense organs are involved in the process of perceiving information by students. Guided by this criterion, didactic means can be divided into visual, auditory, audiovisual, simulators and universal. We can classify the Internet platform as a universal didactic tool, since in the process of perceiving information when learning using the Internet platform, hearing and vision are involved, and certain skills are also practiced with the help of modern simulators (for example, electronic cards with new words).

When understanding a didactic tool as a means of an intangible nature, we are dealing with didactic forms of organizing training, among which traditionally general class forms of organizing classes (lesson, conference, seminar, etc.), group forms of teaching (group work in the lesson, creative tasks) are distinguished. , individual forms of work in the classroom and at home (written exercises, work with literature, etc.) [4]. The capabilities of the Internet platform make it possible to conduct class-wide forms of organizing classes without affecting the quality of education. This is evidenced using webinar platforms for training employees of world-famous companies.

For example, the webinar platform myown-conference.ru can conduct a webinar with one or more presenters and participants in real time, which corresponds to the traditional form of training - a lecture. Group forms of work are usually implemented by creating specific chats between webinar members. Individual works are sent to the group chat or to the e-mail of the seminar leader.

Thus, we can conclude that the Internet platform as a didactic tool is in no way inferior to traditional material didactic means. Organization of training is also possible using the Internet platform without losing the quality of training.

Distance learning undoubtedly has a few advantages over traditional learning. The first and main advantage, of course, is freedom of access. That is, students can study almost anywhere, receiving the quality of education that is only available in big cities. That is, students have equal opportunities regardless of their place of residence. Another very important criterion in favor of choosing distance learning is the opportunity to study with teachers abroad, gain advanced knowledge in scientific fields, attend lectures from the best universities in the world, without incurring significant financial costs for training.

In addition, an important advantage of distance learning is the flexibility of learning. Students of distance courses can adapt the learning process to their needs and choose their own convenient time for learning, which allows adults to study without interrupting their work.

The issue of using distance learning technologies in a foreign language lesson remains open. Even though the Internet platform as a didactic tool is in no way inferior to traditional didactic ones, and allows for all traditional forms of training without loss of quality. However, most modern foreign language teachers still do not choose distance learning.

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